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The Role of Organizational Commitment as a Mediator of Burnout Syndrome and Turnover Intention

Nur Laily¹, Hening Widhi Oetomo², Juwita Sari³, Wimba Respatia⁴

¹ Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya, Indonesia. Email: nurlaily@stiesia.ac.id

² Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya, Indonesia. Email: heningwidio@stiesia.ac.id

³ Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya, Indonesia. Email: juwitasari@stiesia.ac.id

⁴ Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya, Indonesia. Email: wimbarespatia@stiesia.ac.id

Correspondence: Nur Laily. Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA) Surabaya, Indonesia.
Email: nurlaily@stiesia.ac.id

Abstract

Turnover intention is the tendency or intention of employees to stop working from their jobs voluntarily or move from one workplace to another according to their own choice. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of burnout on turnover intentions, the organizational commitment to turnover intentions, and the indirect relationship between burnout and turnover intentions through organizational commitment. This type of research is a quantitative study. The sampling in this study used probabilistic sampling using cluster sampling and simple random sampling. The study population consisted of healthcare professionals from five hospitals in Surabaya as referrals for Covid19 patients. The sample contains 100 respondents. Route analysis by the Smart PLS 2.0 program is used as a data analysis method. The results show that burnout affects turnover intentions. Burnout adversely affects an organization's commitment, which in turn adversely affects the intent of leaving a job. In addition, the results of indirect impact tests show that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between burnout and willingness to leave.

Keywords: Job Insecurity, Burnout, Turnover Intention, Organizational Commitment

1. Introduction

Healthcare professionals are the hospital's most important asset, as hospital activities are impossible to be done without them. The 2019 Coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemic threatens health worldwide. as COVID19 is already prevalent in Indonesia, the government is taking proactive and efficient steps to combat the COVID-19. (Laily et al., 2020). According to World Health Organization (WHO) data on January 26th, 2021, 99,363,697 cases have been identified worldwide. Healthcare professionals who suffer from burnout have a psychological impact on the quality of life and work productivity in the medical sector. Many phenomena occur, one of the burnout effects is the desire to change jobs. According to Wirawan (2015), the intent of leaving a job is the tendency or intention of an employee to voluntarily quit their job based on their own decisions. Robbins & Judge (2013) suggest that if an

employee is happy with the job, it may or may not be completely genuine. Organizations will experience frustration and loss when a talented employee chooses to resign and move to another company.

Burnout continues to be an occupational health and productivity issue by an increasing number of events requiring serious stakeholder attention. Burnout syndrome is one of the stressful conditions related to work. This condition is characterized by physical and emotional fatigue since the expectations and realities of the employee in their position do not work as intended (Rofiqoh, 2021). Maslach and Jackson (Fuente et al., 2015) argue that nurse burnout is a condition that describes the response to chronic work-related stress with three components or dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal achievement. Research conducted by Mansour & Tremblay (2018) showed that burnout affects employee turnover intention.

Organizational commitment is a condition where employees are interested in the goals, values, and goals of their organization (Mowday et al., 1982). Research by Meyer & Allen (1990) suggests that commitment to the company is a psychological condition that can be described or expressed by the relationship between employees and the organization which has implications for the employee's decision to continue or stop being a member of the organization. Reduced employee intention to leave the organization is a result of increased employee engagement. According to Putra & Utama's (2018) research, organizational commitment has a bad effect on employee turnover intention. In addition, the findings of Lestari & Mujiati (2018) show organizational commitment has a significant negative impact on employee turnover intentions.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Turnover Intention

A high turnover rate can have a negative impact on a company. According to Porter (2011), employee turnover can cost a company substantial amount of capital when considering downtime, recruiting, interviewing, orientation, training, and ramp-up time. An entry-level position can cost an organization about 50 to 100 percent of the employee's wage.

Therefore, it is important for businesses to strive to avoid high employee turnover. Additionally, according to Surji (2013), employee turnover is a direct statement of the company, which can be detrimental to customer service and quality. (Bothma & Roodt, 2012) explain that the loss of highly skilled staff will have catastrophic consequences for the organization, such as disruption of organizational functions, service provision, and management.

Turnover intention is the tendency to leave work voluntarily or involuntarily because it is not suitable for the current job. Turnover intention is an early sign of turnover, because there is a significant relationship between turnover intention and employee turnover. Turnover intention can be defined as a deliberate and conscious intention or desire to seek alternative work in other organizations (Tett & Meyer, 1993; Wu, 2012). According to Jacobs & Roodt (2011) turnover intention is a person's intention to leave or quit a job which is a type of withdrawal behavior towards work.

2.2. Burnout Syndrome

Burnout syndrome is caused by prolonged stress. Burnout is a psychological term that describes a state of fatigue from work. This condition is characterized by physical and emotional exhaustion since the expectations and reality of the employee in his position do not work as expected. Burnout is a form of persistent stress and failure to meet expectations (Kartono, 2017: 37). Rosyid and Farhati (in Syamsu et al., 2019) suggest burnout indications are reflected when individuals experience fatigue, cynicism, boredom, emotional exhaustion, and reduced personal accomplishment. There are several indicators to assess burnout as described by Priansa, (2017) namely physical exhaustion, emotional exhaustion, mental exhaustion, low self-esteem, depersonalization. Weisberg (1994) found there was a positive relationship between burnout and turnover intention. El-Sakka (2016) found the burnout variable had a positive relationship with turnover intention. This relationship is evidenced in Sakka's statement that turnover intention plays a role as a consequence of the burnout phenomenon. Liu & Lo (2018) found that

burnout had a significant positive effect on turnover intention. Zhang & Feng (2011) show that burnout has a significant positive effect on turnover intentions.

H₁. Burnout syndrome has a significant positive effect on turnover intentions

2.3. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is a state in which employees have a deep interest in the organization's goals, values, and goals. In addition, an organization's commitment is more than just a formal membership, as it involves an attitude of preference for the organization and a willingness to make a high level of commitment to the interests of the organization to achieve its goals (Porter, 2011). Robbins & Judge (2013) suggest that organizational involvement is enthusiastic. An individual who is willing to stay in an organization in identifying contributions to the organization is exemplified by accepting the organization's vision and mission. Luthans (2011) explains that an organization's commitment as an attitude is often defined as a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization. The willingness to provide a high level of commitment on behalf of the organization and a firm belief and acceptance of the organization's values and goals. Meyer & Allen (1990) develop three aspects of an organization's commitment: emotional commitments and normative commitments first. Luz et al., (2018) Discovered that organizational commitment is the most important determinant of sales intent. Luthans (2011) show that the conclusions of both previous and recent studies have a positive link between organizational involvement and desirable outcomes such as high performance, low turnover, and low absenteeism. It states that it is. According to Mowday et al., (1982), Employees with high organizational commitment have found that they are present in the organization and are more motivated to achieve their organizational goals. High organizational commitment, on the other hand, has a negative impact on employee turnover. The findings of Puangyoykeaw & Nishide (2015) show that organizational involvement influences sales intent.

H₂. Burnout syndrome has a negative effect on organizational commitment

H₃. Organizational commitment has a negative effect on turnover intention

H₄. Organizational Commitment can mediate the relationship between burnout and turnover intention

2.4. Research Model

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Research Method

3.1. Population and samples

This research used a comparative causal research method. Research Population Hospital healthcare professionals in Surabaya who handle COVID-19 referral patients are still actively working. The sample to be used was 100 respondents. In this case, the questionnaire was used as the main primary data which would be used to analyze the research. The measurement scale used in this study is the Likert Scale. namely Strongly Disagree (STS) = 1, Disagree (TS) = 2, Disagree (KS) = 3, Agree (S) = 4, Strongly Agree (SS) = 5

3.2. Research Variable

Organizational commitment is a state in which employees have a deep interest in the organization's goals, values, and goals. Indicators developed by Robbins and Judge (2013) are Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment. Burnout syndrome is a process where there is a change in negative behavior in response to pressure and work stress for a prolonged time. Indicators developed by Baron and Greenberg (in Chairiza et al., 2018): Physical exhaustion, Emotional exhaustion, Mental fatigue, Low self-esteem. Turnover Intention is the tendency or intention of employees to quit from their jobs voluntarily or move from one workplace to another according to their own choice. Indicators developed by Chen & Francesco (2000): Thoughts of leaving current job, Desire to look for other job vacancies, Desire to leave the organization in the coming months. Include in these subsections the information essential to comprehend and replicate the study. Insufficient detail leaves the reader with questions; too much detail burdens the reader with irrelevant information. Consider using appendices and/or a supplemental website for more detailed information.

3.3. Data Analysis

The data analysis used a partial least squares (PLS) approach, a component or variant-based structural equation modeling (SEM). The formal model defines a latent variable as a linear set of indicators. Weight estimates for generating latent variable score components are obtained based on the inner and outer model. Appropriate identification of research participants is critical to the science and practice of psychology, particularly for generalizing the findings, making comparisons across replications, and using the evidence in research syntheses and secondary data analyses. If humans participated in the study, report the eligibility and exclusion criteria, including any restrictions based on demographic characteristics.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Result

The results showed that most of the respondents were women (76.2%). Most of them aged 26-35 years (62.7%), categorized as early adulthood. Most respondents being in early adulthood may appropriately reflect employee turnover intentions. Early adulthood is a period in which employees still have high productivity. When work does not have the opportunity to increase productivity growth, employees will intend to leave. Judging from the level of education, most of the respondents are undergraduates (90.7%). In short, most of the respondents are highly educated.

Education level can influence individuals to make decisions. Based on employment status, most of the respondents were permanent employees (93.7%), and only 6.3% were temporary contract employees. Most respondents have worked for 3 to 4 years (40.5%), and the rest have worked for more than five years. These data are assumed to match the conditions under which fatigue syndrome may occur after prolonged exposure to the task.

Figure 2: PLS Model

The test results in Figure 2 show that the loading factor or outer loading has a value above 0.7. It means that the indicators used in this study are valid or meet convergent validity. The AVE value for each variable tested has a value > 0.5. This indicates that all the variables in this study meet the criteria for discriminant validity. Test results show that the value of each variable in this study exceeds 0.70. Therefore, all variables tested are said to meet the construct reliability.

Table 1: R Square

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Organizational Commitment	0.431	0.426
Turnover Intention	0.328	0.314

Source: processed data

Table 1 shows that latent burnout affects the organizational commitment of the structural model. The R2 value is 0.431, indicating that the model is "strong." Latent variables, burnout, and organizational commitments affect sales intention variables. The R2 value of the structural model is 0.328, indicating that the model is "strong enough."

Table 2: Direct effect

Correlation Between Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Burnout Syndrome to Organizational Commitment	-0.657	0.664	-0.063	10.449	0.000
Burnout Syndrome to Turnover Intention	0.231	0.230	0.117	1.981	0.048
Organizational Commitment to Turnover Intention	0.393	0.398	0.114	0.3450	0.001

Source: primary data processed

The results of the direct impact hypothesis test in Table 2 are as follows: Burnout syndrome has an effect on Turnover intention, so the first hypothesis is accepted. The second hypothesis is accepted because burnout adversely affects the commitment of the organization. The third hypothesis is accepted because organizational commitment negatively impacts turnover intent.

Table 3: Indirect Effect

Indirect Effect Test	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Burnout Syndrome to Organizational Commitment to Turnover Intention	-0.258	0.264	-0.082	3.154	0.002

Source: primary data processed

The indirect effect test in Table 3 shows that Burnout Syndrome has an indirect negative effect on turnover intention. These results indicate that Organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between Burnout Syndrome and Turn Over Intention.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1. Burnout syndrome's Effect on Turnover Intention

Healthcare professionals are tired of their work caring for Covid-19 patients who continue to arrive at the Surabaya Referral Hospital. It can be interpreted that the more the medical staff recognizes the burnout syndrome, the stronger the intention to leave the job. Cordes & Dougherty (1993); Chairiza et al., (2018) theorize the intention of leaving a job is caused by burnout, and when an employee feels burnout, signs appear in the form of increased

headaches, fatigue, inability to complete work, and increased absenteeism. Employees are dissatisfied with their work and are about to change jobs because the negative signs they experience affect their performance (Maslach et al., 2013). When burnout occurs, it reduces engagement so that employees continue to think about making a turnover. The results of this study are consistent with previous studies by Kardiawan & Budiono (2018) who found that burnout had a significant positive effect on the willingness to leave. In addition, it is supported by the findings of Cordes & Dougherty (1993) Burnout states that it has a positive and significant impact on employees' intentions to retire. The result of Masluchah et al., (2020) also agrees that burnout has a significant impact on turnover intentions.

4.2.2. Burnout Syndrome has a negative effect on Organizational Commitment

The results of the hypothesis test show that burnout adversely affects the commitment of the health care worker's organization. In other words, the higher the burnout, the lower the organization's commitment. On the other hand, the lower the burnout, the higher the organizational commitment of the employee. Desperate, making mistakes at work, and often easily angry with patients and colleagues, health care professionals' burnout is still reasonable or not excessive. That's because the company's medical professionals have worked for the company for a long time and still have a very high level of organizational commitment.

According to Edelwich & Brodsky (1980), the final result of the burnout syndrome process is turnover, which includes enthusiasm, stagnation, frustration, apathy, and the last stage is intervention. The intervention stage is the stage where employees decide to leave the organization, switch from work, and adjust work responsibilities.

These results do not support Nugroho et al., (2016) in their research results that burnout has a negative and insignificant effect on organizational commitment

4.2.3. Organizational Commitment has a negative effect on Turnover Intention

The level of organizational commitment is inversely proportional to the level of employee turnover intention. If the healthcare professional has a high degree of organizational commitment, the intention to cancel is low and vice versa. However, the company provides facilities that meet the expectations of healthcare professionals, and the high organizational commitment of healthcare professionals allows him to survive in the company. Healthcare professionals are usually devoted to their profession, not the hospital in which they work. Because wherever healthcare professionals work, the main thing is their duty as healthcare workers to help patients. Mowday et al., (1979) argues that an organization's commitment is relatively strong within the organization and is an identification of an individual's commitment to working hard to achieve the organization's goals. This is in line with the research conducted by Allen & Meyer (1991) which states that organizational commitment has a significant negative relationship to turnover intention

4.2.4. Burnout Syndrome affects Turnover Intention through Organizational Commitment

These results explain that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship from burnout to turnover intention in Health Workers. Organizational commitment suggests organizational commitment is an individual's enthusiasm in identifying his or her contribution to the company, illustrated by the acceptance of the company's vision and mission, willingness, and having the desire to stay at the company (Robbins & Judge, 2015), while Burnout syndrome can be said to be a form of continuous stress and the inability to meet expectations (Kartono, 2017). It can be interpreted that someone who experiences burnout syndrome and decides to leave the company, then employees need organizational commitment as a mediator. This is in line with the research of Santi et al., (2020) which states that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between burnout and turnover intention.

5. Conclusions

Burnout affects the intention of healthcare professionals to leave their jobs, and the higher the awareness of burnout, the higher the intention to leave. However, burnout adversely affects the organizational commitment, and it adversely affects the profit intentions of health care workers. In addition, organizational commitments can

mediate the relationship between burnout and Turnover intention. This means that efforts must be made to reduce turnover intent by minimizing burnout and increasing the organization's commitment through an appropriate compensation system. When dealing with high levels of burnout, employees can take time to think about the cause of the burnout and eliminate it. Organizations can help by telling them that they will prevent them from burning out. We can provide employees with the best solutions to reduce the severity of their burnout. The company is expected to increase employee loyalty by increasing employee engagement. If employees are loyal, employee commitment increases on their own, making it difficult to leave the company even if they get better deals.

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